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Exploring the Strategy, Economic Impact & nexus between Rural Development & Urban Development: Enugu State in Context

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ABSTRACT

The study was focused on exploring the strategy economic impact and nexus between rural development and urban development, using Enugu State as a study base. The strategic methods for economic advancement between rural and urban development in Enugu State is within the framework of political and socio-economic landscapes. The study emphasizes the need for understanding the increasing importance of integrated development planning and implementation strategies, as pathways to bridge the gaps and ensure balanced development between rural – urban dichotomies. Therefore, the paper explores the nexus between rural and urban development, thereby establishing how they relate and influence each other’s growth and operations. The methods use in the study is a qualitative research approach that gathered data through secondary means. The study identified some important key development strategies adopted by rural and urban areas to evaluate the income, labour and services rendered. The Endogenous Growth Theory, developed by Paul Romer was employed in the analysis. Findings show that rural underdevelopment is the main reason for rural – urban migration, overpopulation of urban areas, infrastructural gaps, and economic imbalances prevalent in the two economies. The study recommended that the government should invest in rural infrastructure, such as good roads, electricity, schools, hospitals, security, and communication networks. These improvements when achieved will enhance connectivity, enabling rural producers to access urban markets with ease, ultimately fostering growth and link-ups in both rural and urban economies. This will also attract more investments to rural areas.

Keywords: Rural-urban development, economic growth, administration, Enugu State

INTRODUCTION

People are moving daily in large numbers from rural to urban areas in Nigeria. Thus, urban centers or cities are growing rapidly and getting overcrowded. People migrate from rural to urban areas due to limited access to educational opportunities, infrastructure, and limited job opportunities. Urban centers typically gain importance when a country's development rate rises because this is where a country's capabilities are most clearly displayed (Ahmed et al, 2021). Given that the majority of developing nations are only just beginning their industrialisation, the patent deduction based on the historical development of the Western world, which shows that urbanisation and industrialisation are correlated, indicates the obvious fact that continued rapid urbanisation in developing nations is unavoidable. According to Oluwatoyin (2023), rural-urban inequality in wealth leads to rural-urban migration as a result of people looking for perceived or actual chances for better livelihoods.

Urban and rural areas comprise almost half of the nation's population of around 189 million people (United Nations, 2018). The proportion of Nigerians living in urban areas increased from 15.41% in 1960 to 49.52% in 2017 (UN 2018). The two verifiable variables that have combined to make this a reality are high rates of urban births and migration from rural to urban areas (Chigbu, 2013). Still, there are other important considerations. For example, Nigeria has maintained a dichotomous relationship between rural and urban areas since the establishment of a formal planning system. Urban and rural areas are perceived as difference from one another. In Enugu State, rural areas are often larger than urban areas and have a more traditional character. More infrastructure is "normally" present in urban, including roads, schools, employment, healthcare, retail, and industries, among many other things. Migration from rural to urban areas has become major criteria in the expansion of the urban growth.

Enugu state rural areas make a significant contribution to the state GDP through agriculture. Over 70% to 80% of livelihood-earning occupations in Enugu State are in agricultural, and over 20% of the state GDP has come from this sector periodically.(Lion Building watch December 2024). But, they are still largely isolated from the state essential services for a good quality of life (Chigbu, 2013). Gender inequality, tenure insecurity, women's disempowerment, inadequate land interventions for development, cultural loss, and poverty are some of the specific land-related issues that are inherent in rural areas (Chigbu and Klaus, 2013; Chigbu, 2015; Chigbu et al., 2018/2019).

Rural development and urban development are increasingly recognized as interconnected and mutually supportive, with each sector supporting the other. For city industrial and economic operations, rural regions provide vital resources like labour, raw materials, and agricultural outputs. On the other hand, urban areas provide marketplaces, enhance demand for rural goods, and allow for technology and infrastructure spillovers that can spur rural development (Tacoli, 2023). Investments in rural development, especially in the areas of infrastructure, health, and education, as the state government is pushing is to lessen the pressures of rural-urban migration and increase agricultural and cottage industry production. In addition to stabilizing rural economies, this establishes a foundation for balanced regional development that promotes long-term urban growth (World Bank, 2022). The prosperity of rural communities contributes to national food security and a stable supply chain for urban manufacturing, which in turn decreases the cost of living in urban areas and increases disposable income and consumption patterns (UNDP, 2023).

Significant rural development initiatives have recently been launched by Enugu State with the goal of improving infrastructure and agricultural output, which will support urban economic growth. The "One Political Ward, One Farm Estate" One Green Smart School programme is a noteworthy endeavour that has been allocated billions of Naira to create agricultural estates in each of the 260 political and electoral wards and the children from rural areas to have a better education. (Nairametric, to 2025). In order to attain self-sufficiency and improve food security, this programme aims to teach locals contemporary agronomic techniques and encourage a variety of farming pursuits, such as crop production and animal husbandry. The improvement of infrastructure has also been given top priority. N183 billion was authorised by the Enugu state government to build 20 rural and 141 urban roads (Lion Building Watch March 2025). These initiatives seek to boost economic activity in both rural and urban areas, increase connectivity, and make it easier for agricultural products to reach urban markets. Food shortages will be addressed, and the state's objective of growing significant amounts of staple crops each year will be supported.

By consistent supply of agricultural products, lowering the cost of food, and generating employment opportunities, these rural development initiatives by Enugu State government is geared towards anticipation to make a substantial contribution to the economic growth of Enugu urban. Better rural infrastructure makes it easier for items to be transported to cities efficiently, which boosts trade and business. Agro-industries may be drawn to cities by higher agricultural production, which would further stimulate the economy of Enugu State.

Statement of the Problem

Despite with Enugu State's efforts to boost rural development through capacity-building programmes, infrastructure upgrade, and agricultural initiatives, the anticipated benefits to urban economic growth remain inconsistent and unrealised. Rural areas have significant agricultural potential and labour, but development is hindered by inadequate infrastructure, limited markets, restricted financial services, and weak links between rural production and urban markets. In order to bridge the existing gap

between the rural and urban experiences, Enugu State government share farming tools and materials to local farmers to boost the economy (Sahara Reporter 2024).

High cost of food items, job searching, and crowded economic activity are still problems in Enugu City, showing obvious reasons that the current rural development initiative programmes have not successfully metamorphosed into long-term urban economic growth. The underutilization of rural resources and the influx of rural – urban migration have led to disparities in population distribution, resource allocation, and economic possibilities opportunities.

Furthermore, there is little empirical data evaluating the state's successful implementation of notable initiatives like "One Ward, One Farm Estate" One Green Smart School and Type A hospital and large-scale rural road construction projects in terms of boosting urban economic productivity. This disparity raises questions regarding these projects' long-term effects, inclusivity, and sustainability.

A comprehensive study is needed to explore the connection between rural development projects and urban economic expansion in Enugu State, considering the interdependence between rural and urban areas. This investigation would help understand how initiatives in rural settings can impact economic growth in urban centres, ultimately informing policies that foster sustainable development across Enugu State.

Methodology

A descriptive survey design was used in this investigation. This method utilizes a qualitative process of organizing data from literature to find variables and their relationships. As a result, it gives the appropriate framework or blueprint for addressing the research gaps. The area of the study is Enugu State. The dependent and independent variables are rural development, urban development and economy of Enugu State. The independent and dependent variables were analyzed to streamline the content of this paper on the nexus between rural and urban development. Secondary data emanated from textbooks, journals articles, newspapers, and internet materials, government publications etc, were gathered and descriptively content analyzed to arrive at the findings and the conclusion drawn

Theoretical Framework

The Endogenous Growth Theory was primarily developed by Paul Romer (1990). The theory emphasizes that economic growth is driven by factors within the economy, such as technology, knowledge, and human capital. The key tenets of this theory include human capital, technological innovation, and knowledge as central drivers of sustained economic growth. Unlike classical growth theories, which focus on external factors such as capital accumulation, endogenous growth theory argues that investments in knowledge, education, and innovation create a self-sustaining process of growth.

One fundamental tenet of the theory is that human capital, or the skill and knowledge possessed by the workforce, directly influences productivity and economic expansion. Romer suggests that human capital investment leads to the creation of new ideas and innovations, which in turn boost productivity and economic output.

Another important tenet is the concept of increasing returns to scale, where the more resources allocated to knowledge and technology, the greater the potential for sustained growth. This theory also asserts that government policies supporting research, development, and education are crucial in fostering long-term economic growth, particularly in both rural and urban areas. By focusing on internal factors, Endogenous Growth Theory provides insights into how human capital and innovation can drive regional development, especially in the context of rural-urban dynamics.

Application of the theory

The application of this theory suggests that investments in education, infrastructure, and technological innovations in rural areas can lead to higher productivity and, in turn, contribute to urban economic growth. It supports the idea that the development of human capital and technological advancements in rural areas can spill over into urban areas, enhancing economic activities and productivity in urban cities. Endogenous growth theory, therefore, underscores the need to foster development in an economy, especially rural economy from looking inward and using available resources within the people and the environment to build capabilities that will drive social economic development and production capacity of an economy. These no doubt are achieved through education, skills acquisitions, and investment in population quality and health of the people that promote human capital

development, upon which material resources and the environment are harnessed to build a robust return on investments and development in an economy. Harnessing the endogenous potentials in any rural economy will facilitate building and developing the economy, and consequently stem the tides of rural – urban migration, gaps in rural – urban infrastructures, dichotomy and a lack of balanced development often witnessed between rural and urban economies.

Literature Review

Rural development

The definition of rural development hasn't always been clear. However, it is generally seen as a comprehensive idea that acknowledges the intricacy and interdependence of the several factors affecting rural residents' quality of life (Uyanga, 1980). Over time rural communities experience both measurable and non - measurable changes that together improve quality of life and living standards. Agricultural production significantly contributes to this progress but rural development, and agricultural development are distinct concepts and should not be used interchangeably.

Increasing the standard of living for the vast majority of low-income people who live in rural areas and enabling their development to be self-sustaining has been a popular idea in rural development (Uyanga, 1980).

The concept has three key crucial elements that greatly impact the design and implementation of rural development projects:

(a) improving rural residents living standards, requires mobilisation and allocating resources to strike a balance between the welfare and productive services in the rural sector; (b) support large number of participation, by necessitating that resources distributed to low-income areas and classes and that social and productive services truly get to them; and

(c) ensuring the process is self-sustaining, which calls for the establishment of institutions at the local, regional, and national levels as well as the development of the necessary skills and implementation capacity to guarantee the efficient use of current resources and to encourage the mobilisation of additional financial and human resources for the rural sector's ongoing development. Here, self-sustenance means engaging the rural population through rural development programmes, as opposed to merely contacting them (Uyanga, 1980).

The goal of the multifaceted idea of rural development is to raise the standard of living and financial security of those who reside in rural regions. Rural development, according to Todaro and Smith (2020), entails tactics meant to raise rural residents' incomes and productivity by giving them access to modern agricultural practices, infrastructure, healthcare, and education. According to the World Bank (2021), rural development is an all-encompassing strategy aimed at lowering rural poverty through improving access to markets, necessary services, and sustainable means of subsistence.

Olayide et al. (2022) state that intentional policies and initiatives aimed at improving rural communities through better road systems, agriculture, and human capital development constitute rural development in Nigeria. Akin to this, Aremu and Alabi (2023) contend that rural development involves enabling communities to take part in local government and decision-making processes in addition to physical infrastructure.

Urban Economic Growth

"Urban economic growth" refers to the rise in wealth, productivity, and economic activities that occurs in urban cities driven by industrialisation, technical advancement, and the growth of the service sector. Agglomeration economies, in which companies and industries concentrate in urban areas, promote innovation and generate employment possibilities, are mostly responsible for urban economic growth, according to Glaeser (2021). Economic expansion is facilitated by this process, which increases the amount of infrastructure, labour, and capital.

Urban economic growth, according to the United Nation UN (2020), is the growth of urban economies through greater trade, investment, and infrastructure, as well as through improved institutional capacity and human capital. According to the World Bank (2022), effective public service delivery, improved educational access, and integration into international supply chains are all associated with urban economic growth in developing economies.

Similarly, Roberts and Sykes (2023) contend that the transition from basic industries to higher-value sectors like technology, finance, and services—all of which demand skilled labour and promote sustainable urban development—is a necessary component of urban economic growth.

Income and Spending Capacity

The income of individuals or households in urban areas, encompassing profits, salaries wages, and other types of financial benefits, are referred to as urban income. Chatterjee and Bhattacharya (2021) assert that the concentration of firms, industries, and service sectors that offer a wide variety of revenue-generating options shapes urban income. Variables like education, manpower levels, and the available of well-paying jobs in industries like manufacturing, technology, and finance are frequently correlated with urban income.

According to Lichtenstein and Petersen (2022), spending capacity is the amount of money that urban dwellers can spend on goods and services, depending on their income levels, access to credit, and consumption habits. The economic might of urban populations and their influence on regional and national economies are reflected in this idea. The Organisation for Economic Co –operation and Development OECD (2023) states that urban spending power is also influenced by housing, transportation, and living expenses, all of which differ between cities.

Employment rate

The employment rate, is a key labour market indicator, measures the percentage of the working-age population (usually those between the ages of 15 and 64) that is employed. The employment rate, according to Blanchard (2022), indicates how well an economy is using its labour force; a greater employment rate denotes improved economic conditions and the creation of jobs.

The ratio of employed people to the working-age population, excluding those who are actively looking for work but are having difficulty finding it, is known as the employment rate, according to the International Labour Organisation (ILO) (2021). It is a crucial indicator for evaluating both the effectiveness of labour laws and the state of the economy. In developing countries, employment rates can also highlight disparities in job opportunities, with factors like education, gender, and access to labour markets influencing outcomes (Klasen, 2023). According to ILO (2022), measuring the employment rate provides valuable insights into the efficiency of labor market policies and economic growth strategies.

Business Establishment Growth

Business establishment growth involves increasing of businesses size, revenue, market presence, and workforce. According to Davidson and Wiklund (2021), business establishment growth can be measured by the increase in the number of businesses, the scale of operations, and profitability over time. Growth is often driven by factors such as innovation, market demand, access to capital, and effective management strategies.

According to the World Bank (2022), business establishment growth in developing economies is often linked to improvements in the business environment, such as infrastructure, regulatory frameworks, and financial access. This growth is necessary for job opportunities and enhancing local economies.

López and Rodríguez (2023) emphasize that business establishment growth is influenced by both internal factors, such as entrepreneurial skills, and external factors, including market competition and governmental support.

Impact of rural development on urban development

Rural development plays important roles on urban development

1. **Food Security:** Rural development are the major source of food availability in urban centers, this is achieved through ensuring steady supply of food to urban centers. Without rural food production, many urban centers will not survive, the impact of rural food production to urban areas cannot be overemphasized. FAO (2023).
2. **Job/Labour Market:** Because of job opportunities in urban areas rural development lead to spontaneous migration of workers to urban centers, increasing and contributing to urban economic advancement.
3. **Market Availabilities:** Rural development creates new markets because of the products, and by so doing creating new market opportunities for urban businesses like tourism, entertainment industry boom, agricultural produces and agro – processing goods.

4. Environmental Sustainability: Rural areas have land mass for cultivation and rearing of livestock. They sustain land use and its natural resources thereby benefitting urban areas by preventing environmental pollution/degradation.
5. Remittance: Rural development fosters enhance remittance from urban centers, thereby encouraging rural livelihoods and supporting to local economic growth.
6. Supply of raw materials to industries: Raw materials used in producing finished goods in urban industries are produced in the rural areas and transport to the urban centers, where they are utilized in manufacturing and industrializes sector of the urban economy.

The nexus between rural development and urban economic development

Both are linked in economics, social and environment principles that drives the existence of rural and urban cooperation, the urban centres determines the prospect of rural areas, through consumption and market, most goods and services are produced in urban cities such as electronics, wears/clothing, cinema, quality education thereby making it almost impossible for the rural to survive without urban, in the other hand the urban cities largely depend on rural areas for food items, water, raw materials to run their factories to produce goods and render services. Industries are homed in urban centre with its services, rural areas are dependent on manufactured products, such as farm tools, fertilizers and textiles to operate at their local level. The issues in Rural and Urban Development in Enugu State border on rural poverty, inadequate funding of programmes, corruption in government, lack of local government full autonomy, rural and community development programmes, rural-urban migration, lack of continuity of programmes, and over-politicization of development matters, amongst others. Odo and Aidelokhai (2022).

The opportunities to develop rural areas in Enugu State can be tailored towards entrepreneurship schemes by getting people involved in urbanization through the potentials of rural endowment utilization. Infrastructure services are mostly in urban area through the expansion which often lead to the extension of roads, internet, rural facilitate trading and access to service delivery. Environmental relationship entails that urban demand impact on land use, deforestation for agricultural produce and the waste from urban areas and pollutions degenerate rural environment thereby causing health challenges. Harnessing urbanization potential closely tied to entrepreneurship can significantly boost rural development in Enugu State. Local development initiatives should leverage available resources local skills, traditional production method and social networks to drive sustainable development and to unlock internal growth potential. The policy of government both national and state coordinates on their interactions, planning development, which should reduce rural and urban disparities that will balance both development simultaneously

Despite Agriculture and its potential to boost the economy of Enugu State by the current government, the production linkage between both is that rural produce and supply to urban areas which is the evidence of rural support to urban, while corporate agriculture remains underfunded and underutilized. Migration from rural to urban have provided labour for urban companies and households, while the occasional migration has permitted households to diversify their income through payments. Financial inflows from the urban areas such as banks invest in rural development projects and rural saving enhance capital formation and demand in Enugu city. Government policies have hindered large scale investment, instead prioritizing official funding programmes that are vulnerable to mismanagement and waste. This has led to significant consequences, including unemployment, food insecurity, and rural poverty.

Evaluating the strategies for rural – urban development

The Government of Enugu State in its efforts to strengthen the gap between rural – urban development need to evaluates strategies that improve on the connection of both economies.

1. Comprehensive Growth: Evaluating strategies of rural – urban development emphasis that growth should be inclusive and holistic thereby ensuring that each sector benefits are shared equitable resources among the stakeholders to foster/enhance growth simultaneously in the two rural – urban economies.
2. Integration: Rural – urban development strategies are the key for integration that will encourage interdependence among the rural and urban cities. Integration of both sectors will

sustain collaboration that will provide effectiveness in food production, and accelerated economic growth through forward and backward economic linkages.

3. Sustainability: Environmental conservation should be crucial for consideration in rural – urban development strategies. It will help to sustain increase in food production, enhance livelihoods and reduce poverty per head count.
4. Local Context: Strategies per local context should be considered by taking into account the necessary measures like culture, geography, political and economic conditions of the place that will promote effective communication and reduce migration to urban areas. That is creating the need to recognize and harmonize the unique comparative advantage of each sector. This, no doubt, will yield maximum operations and benefits in localized production of good and services, and development of human capital according to the requirements of each environment.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The research shows that rural development has a notable impact on the income and purchasing power of city dwellers in Enugu Metropolis. Better rural infrastructure, like roads and utilities, will boost connection between rural suppliers and urban markets, making goods more available and affordable in urban areas. This, in turn, consequently urban residents enjoy greater buying power. Investing in rural education and skill development will create a more skilled workforce, many of whom move to urban areas for better jobs, thereby increasing urban income levels and purchasing power. Rural development, sparks small and medium enterprises (SMEs) growth creating new markets and opportunities for urban businesses driving economic activity and increasing urban residents' income. This emphasizes the integration of rural development and urban economic prosperity in Enugu Metropolis.

Advancement in rural infrastructure, like access roads and good public utilities, will improve connectivity between rural producers and urban markets. Rural connection allows rural people to participate in trade, creating more jobs in the city. Furthermore, investments in rural education and hands-on - training equip persons with skills that are transferable to urban industries, thereby strengthening employment rates in Enugu Metropolis.

Development initiatives fueling rural small and medium enterprises (SMEs), proliferation also contribute to urban job creation. These small and medium enterprises expand their branches to urban centers, creating jobs and enhancing economic activities. Furthermore, addressing problems like inadequate government support, unlimited credit facilities and improper business planning affects sustainability and growth of SMEs in Enugu State. Government policies have affected operation of SMEs in Enugu Metropolis that has led to the closure of some businesses due to not meeting up with government taxes and other demands. In a nutshell, holistic rural development strategies—encompassing infrastructure improvement, educational advancement, and SME support—play a vital role in promoting employment rates in Enugu Metropolis.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that a strong rural development and urban development nexus increase well balanced structured development paradigm that will reduce inequality and stimulate economic resilience, policy integration and inclusive planning are crucial to harness the collaboration/synergies between rural and urban plays a crucial role in shaping the economic. Building new infrastructure, standardizing education, and promoting small business enterprises, rural development will enhance economic activities in urban centers like Enugu Metropolis. The cohesion of rural and urban areas, highlighting the need for collaboration will promote sustainable growth and improve the income, employment, and business climate in both.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following were recommended

- i. It is recommended that the government should invest in rural infrastructure, like good roads network, electricity with friendly billings, and communication networks. These advancements will improve connectivity, enabling rural producers to access urban markets, promoting growth in both rural and urban economies. This will also attract more investments to rural areas.

- ii. Government policies should be prioritizing rural small and medium enterprise SMEs with resources and support to boost economic development. There is need for credit facilities, training, and market opportunities to be expanded. Growing rural businesses through innovation will contribute to urban economic buoyance by providing new goods and services.
- iii. Educational and Vocational Training should be the key components of rural development initiatives. Rural residents equipped with urban job skills will supply a talented workforce to Enugu city boosting it economies. This will stimulate productivity and affect positively employment rates and economic growth in Enugu Metropolis.

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